

EVALUATING EQUITY OF URBAN AIR MOBILITY ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS: INSIGHTS FROM THE MUSE PROJECT

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Abstract: *This paper presents research results developed within the SESAR MUSE (Measuring U-Space Social and Environmental Impact) project. The goal of MUSE is to develop performance indicators, methods, and tools for the comprehensive assessment of Urban Air Mobility (UAM) impacts on the population in European cities. As part of this effort, the MUSE U-space Environmental and Social Performance Framework was created, comprising 41 indicators across 8 focus areas (noise, visual pollution, privacy concerns, access and equity, economic aspects, emissions, public safety, and wildlife). The framework allows high-resolution impact assessment across spatial, temporal, demographic, socioeconomic and behavioural dimensions. This paper focuses on the “Access and Equity” performance indicators. A novel simulation toolset developed in MUSE was applied to a parcel delivery case study in Madrid. To evaluate equity, we use deviation-based metrics: the relative deviation of each grid cell (zone) exposure from the mean, and the average inequity, calculated as the mean of absolute deviation for all affected zones. The obtained results reveal how drone-based noise and visual pollution exposures differ across zones, making them essential for detecting spatial inequalities. These findings support the development of mitigation strategies and U-space policies, contributing to improved performance monitoring and stronger public acceptance of UAM.*

Keywords: *Urban Air Mobility, social acceptance, unmanned aircraft, drone, performance indicators, access and equity.*

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